

Figure S4. Correlation between the rel. abundance of *Eggerthella lenta* and the cum. levodopa dose [mg] at the top for both groups. Correlation between the rel. abundance of *Enterococcus faecalis* and the cum. levodopa dose [mg] at the bottom for both groups.